

**FROM THE SCIENTIFIC APPROACHES OF EASTERN SCIENTISTS IN
THE STUDY OF PERSONAL CULTURAL AND SPIRITUAL
REQUIREMENTS**

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Abstract: *One of the important aspects of the concept of building a spiritual space and building an enlightened state in new Uzbekistan is the study and analytical formation of the cultural and spiritual requirements of a person. In this regard, medieval scholars of the East conducted fundamental research. For example, in the scientific legacy of our great scientists Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Abu Rayhan Beruni, great attention is paid to the issue of enlightened education of the individual. It has been studied in specific examples that a lot of attention is paid to issues of requirement in the spiritual and cultural development of a person. The article also analyzes the issue of the importance of harmony of “individual-society-state” interests in the spiritual development of society in the period of globalization that is rapidly increasing.*

Key words: *Eastern scholars, culture, spirituality, enlightened society, educational development, new spiritual space, social activity, education and culture, globalization.*

The essence of a person is manifested in his desire for freedom and constant self-improvement. The interest and demands of every person to acquire knowledge, to work, to form the qualities of a spiritually mature person in him regularly motivates him to act. At the same time, personal perfection becomes a factor of priority for the development of any state and society. This situation determines the image of the world history, the enlightened world formed over thousands of years.

In general, the main sign, characteristic aspect of the enlightened world is characterized by individual intelligence, high spiritual world, social morality of this society. However, in recent times, complex internal and external reasons have had an impact on the formation of the spiritual world of the individual and the improvement of the norms of social morality of the society. “It is clear to all of us,” says the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, “today there is a sharp struggle and competition in the world”.

The conflict of interests is increasing in the world. The processes of globalization are creating new opportunities for humanity, but also unexpected problems. Threats and dangers against national identity and moral values are increasing. Vices such as self-centeredness, light-heartedness towards life, work, family, and consumerism are instilled in the minds of the population, especially young people who still cannot distinguish between “black and white” in different ways. The threat of threats such as terrorism, extremism, transnational and cyber crime, human trafficking, and drug trafficking is increasing more and more. In fact, such threats are increasing day by day. In such a situation, it is necessary to keep our people safe and strengthen the process of national identity awareness. One of the most important ways to ensure socio-spiritual stability in society is to develop effective mechanisms for the formation and satisfaction of spiritual and cultural requirements of people, especially young people.

At this point, we consider it appropriate to first of all understand the meaning of terms such as requirement, spirituality, spiritual and cultural requirement. The word “requirement” means requirement, necessity, demand, requirement. The term requirement is an object of special research in all social and humanitarian sciences. Because this concept allows us to make the most reliable, scientifically based conclusions about the origin, formation, and evolution of each science. The history of the origin of the concept of requirement is very ancient. The development of science and the emergence of various civilizations can be felt in the ancient East, especially in our country. Emergence of high spiritual and educational teachings is a product of requirements. It is known that the main rules of the Zoroastrian religion of national and universal importance are described in “Avesta”. In ancient times, the powerlessness of people before the forces of nature, the absence of social unity, the

constant bloodshed as a result of wars between clans, mass immorality – all this began to demand from mankind to believe in certain values. And this belief happened out of necessity. Belief in Zoroastrian religion – our devoted ancestors honored Mother Earth, which is the main source of human life and livelihood, every inch of her soil with great love and did not allow it to become impure.

Our ancestors bowed down to mother earth, fire, soil, and water with all their bodies. The earth, which is considered as a mine of inexhaustible jewels, a treasure of total pleasures, the idol of our shoulders, the land that fills our bellies, the soil, they recognized it as holy, they appreciated it, they honored it. All of these were created as a result of the human requirement to live and aspire to a higher level. Since ancient times, people have seen the way of their development in material well-being, spiritual perfection, living as a community. This undoubtedly led to the emergence of social requirements. Abu Nasr Farabi writes the following about this: "Each person is structured in such a way that he requires many things in order to live and reach the highest level of maturity. He cannot get these things alone, he requires a team of people to get them. Therefore, it is only through the union of many people who are necessary for living, who supply people to each other and help each other, that a person can reach the maturity that his nature aspires to. The activities of the members of such a community as a whole provide each of them with what is necessary for survival and maturity. Therefore, human individuals multiplied and settled on the inhabited part of the earth, resulting in the human community". Our great thinker Abu Nasr Farabi states in his work "Philosophy of Aristotle" that Aristotle studied human spiritual requirements by connecting them with the principle of goodness. It is noted that Aristotle explains that there are four ends that people consider and strive for as virtues that surpass all other desires. These are: the health of the body, the health of the senses (organs), the health of the ability to perceive different things (this is the health because this ability exists), the health of the ability to aspire (this is the health because of the existence of this ability).

Today, Uzbekistan has set itself the goal of establishing a democratic, sovereign, legal, social and secular state.

The most important factor in achieving these ambitious goals is to build a socialized society. In an open, democratic society, the emergence of the ability of a person to demonstrate his talents, their socialization, meeting the requirements reflected in various normative documents adopted by this society, following social values, and getting rid of the state of alienation from society and the state, the spiritual requirements of each person have priority. requires giving. This increases the social importance of spiritual requirements. Scholars of the East paid special attention to this issue. “Each person”, says Abu Nasr Farabi, “according to his nature, requirements many things (clothing, food, housing, books, teachers, friends) to fulfill his requirements and grow”. A person cannot create all the necessary things by himself, in order to find them, he requirements the services of people of various professions. Other people are in the same situation. Humans requirement to integrate into communities and societies to fulfill their requirements and grow. In this community, each person learns the professions that suit his nature, talent and ability, and tries to perfect his art (craft) every day. Therefore, people living in different places (of different nationalities and religions) unite in different societies.

Abu Ali Ibn Sina connects spiritual requirements with human desire for beauty. He said that the means to achieve beauty is love, and perfection comes from nurturing one’s ego. These ideas are described in Ibn Sina’s “Risolai fil ishq”, which describes the origin of the world, the existence of inter-phenomenal harmony and cause-and-effect relationships, the manifestation of the First (God Almighty) (manifestation in the phenomena of the world), the divine order in the universe and universal harmony. It is seen as an expression on the surface of the earth. All things in the universe, by their very essence, strive for perfection, and this striving is said to be a power that originates from the essence of the Xayri Mutloq (God). In fact, spiritual requirements are a social phenomenon formed by a person's requirement for his own perfection. When we mean perfection, our thinkers-scholars first of all took into account such processes as human education, his adherence to values accepted in society, and respect for procedures. Ibn Sina affirmed the priority of spiritual values over other blessings, and considered the desire for wealth and gold and silver, which destroys the soul, and the requirement for various sexual pleasures as obstacles to the spiritual perfection of a person. Abu Rayhan Beruni sees spiritual

requirements in harmony with the emergence of society and the desire of people to live in mutual cooperation. From this point of view, Beruni explains that the reason for the emergence of human society is the natural requirement of conscious beings to live together with each other. Because people are required to live as a community to meet their requirements and to survive in the struggle against the forces of nature. Therefore, Beruni considers it a natural and legal process for people to live in an association (gang), strive for mutual cooperation and help each other. The requirements of people differ from the requirements of ordinary animals by their diversity and abundance of species. A person cannot meet all his requirements alone. "That's why", Beruni writes, "a person requires the cooperation of several more people". The variety and variety of requirements requires an association (group) of several people to satisfy them. For this reason, people are required to establish cities".

We think that it is appropriate to pay attention to another important issue here. The point is that there are always more requirements, including spiritual requirements, than ways and means to satisfy them. This situation, without a doubt, causes certain social disagreements in the society. As a person progresses, his desire for perfection increases. The requirement always precedes the process of satisfying it.

If the growing requirements are not met in time and quality, in such a situation there will be an imbalance between the individual and the society. Therefore, in any society striving for social and moral stability, ensuring this balance and achieving harmony of interests is one of the most important issues. According to our thinkers, the reasons for the abundance of requirements and the lack of means to satisfy them force a person to unite with other conscious beings.

Each person begins to engage in a certain type of work in order to satisfy requirements through mutual cooperation. In other words, the result of primary labor is measured by the amount of means of subsistence necessary to satisfy requirements.

However, due to the fact that the dimensions of the means of subsistence correspond to each other, the requirements of people for work and means of

subsistence are not the same. In order to accurately determine the value of labor and the requirement for means of livelihood, people come to an agreement-compromise regarding the valuation of both and the determination of their respective equivalents. There is some flexibility in determining the dimensions of material requirements. However, it is very difficult to determine the issue of spiritual requirements and the dimensions of their satisfaction. In the Uzbek national value system, the issue of spiritual requirements is more studied in harmony with morality and the concept of a perfect person.

In Uzbek ethics, it is also used in the sense that the foundation of morality is mercy, forgiveness and patience, and to restrain the ego when this social phenomenon arouses lust and anger. Shaykh Muhammad Sadiq Muhammad Yusuf says: Since ancient times, the scholars of ethics have asked, “Are the morals in a person created during his creation, or does a person learn morals later?” They disagreed in answering the question. Some of them say: “Be it good or bad, morals are created when a person is created. Morality cannot be acquired later. Another group of scholars of ethics says: “When a person is born, he is born without any virtues or vices. “What kind of character he has, will appear after birth”. Muslim scholars of moral science say: “The leaven of some morals from the parents is transferred to a person when he is lying in the womb of his mother as a fetus. Allah, the Exalted, creates a human being by adding moral ability to it. In the process of birth and growth, a person develops or loses this or that morality as a result of upbringing, environment and habituation”, they say.

Looking at the matter from this point of view, morality, as well as immorality, begins to form in the process of development of each person in the mother’s womb. However, its full formation occurs gradually, along with the step towards maturity of a person. The presence of morality in a certain level and the desire to develop it appear on the basis of the spiritual requirements of each individual. The formation of the moral system that forms the basis of spiritual requirements in a person depends on many factors.

In our opinion, the first and most important factor is related to the environment in which the student is being educated. To the extent that the environment is

connected with a strong socialization process, then it is possible to achieve a certain goal in this matter. In this, the Uzbek family, neighborhood, kinship ties, socio-spiritual environment created during study and work play the main roles. In the Uzbek national education system, in the process of the formation of spiritual requirements, one of the most important issues is the issue of perfect human education. Aziziddin Nasafi considers two things as a sign of perfection.

One of them is morality, and the other is self-awareness. Depending on the presence or absence of these two bases, he divided people into three groups. The first are people who are not decorated with moral qualities and do not know themselves. The second is people who are decorated with moral qualities, but do not know themselves. The third is always people who are decorated with moral qualities and know themselves. According to the scientist, this next – the third category of people are perfect people.

In the formation of spiritual requirements of the members of the society, great attention is paid to learning and gathering knowledge. People differ from each other not by their material wealth, but by the level of their spiritual wealth. The value of a person is determined by his knowledge, sincerity and intelligence. A learned person is respected everywhere: “The more knowledgeable you are and the more intelligent you are, the more you will be respected”. Just as food is necessary for the development of the body, knowledge is also necessary for the development of human spirituality. A person can find the right way of life only with the help of knowledge. Knowledge illuminates the path of man. Thanks to it, people overcome various qualities and difficulties: “Do not go on a long and unknown journey without knowledge. A person who does not have the light of knowledge will certainly not be able to live peacefully. It should be noted that our thinkers-scholars created a unique doctrine on the issue of the perfect person and morality. The basis of this teaching is the age-old values such as keeping the morals of the sect, not being afraid of smoking, being merciful, being satisfied with a halal bite, being generous, and building all activities on the basis of science. In this sense, there are both scientific and practical reasons to say that a unique code of ethics has been created in our country. At the current stage of the country’s social development, further development of the state and society depends on the education of people, especially

young people, on the extent to which their spiritual requirements are formed and satisfied. It should be noted separately that every society has a practice of organizing its spiritual life based on its own requirements. It is true that there is an educational system common to all eras of social development, which has become a national value among our people after being polished in a traditional way.

However, the revolutionary and evolutionary changes in the political-ideological base and infrastructure of the society as a result of the innovations, socio-political events of the time and space require the spiritual values specific to this period. Society itself creates its own system of spiritual requirements based on this demand. The socio-spiritual stability of any society depends on the extent to which the cultural and spiritual requirements of the citizens are satisfied in this country. For this, first of all, it is necessary to pay attention to the issue of harmony of the interests of the individual, society and the state. The most optimal opportunity to master the masterpieces of culture and art, and to enjoy them more and more widely, can appear only on the basis of the principle of people – society – state. Today, on the basis of the establishment of New Uzbekistan, this principle is being formed. This is reflected in the formation and satisfaction of healthy spiritual and cultural requirements of our people.

From this point of view, spiritual scientist A. Erkayev notes that the praxeological (teaching on the effectiveness of practical action methods of praxeology) content and tasks of spirituality are once again manifested in the protection of their interests by stimulating the healthy requirements of people and society, and bringing them into balance. It is known that high aspirations of a person are related to spirituality, and base desires are related to lack of spirituality.

Relationships built on the basis of spirituality ease the life of a person and society, strengthen humanity, honesty, mutual respect, trust, kindness, mutual support, and community. Gradually, social relations begin to be freed from violence. Relieving social and interpersonal relations from violence, developing tolerance and humanizing them is one of the important praxeological tasks of spirituality. Of course, the issue of spiritual requirements has both theoretical and practical importance. Its theoretical importance is to determine the place of this situation in

the life of an individual and society, to purify the nation and society from a socio-spiritual, ideological and ideological point of view, to achieve the balance of the interests of the individual, society, and the state in this regard. Practical significance is the phenomenon related to the development of the most effective and acceptable methods of formation of spiritual requirements among individuals and society in a broad sense and ensuring their actual realization. In fact, as we mentioned above, one of the most important aspects of the spiritual life of society is the issue of spiritual and cultural requirements. These requirements form the basis of spiritual life, its genetic essence. At this point, it should be noted that with the increasing attention of the state to social issues, spiritual requirements become a separate, independent component of the development of society. It is known that it is important to pay special attention to the relationship between cultural and spiritual activities and spiritual requirements within the scope of the studied topic.

Cultural activity is a state achieved as a result of regulation and coordination of the efforts of individuals and society towards the development of the state and nation. Historically, cultural activity is a social phenomenon that is formed by expressing one's own relations and inner feelings in relation to this situation, even in the crisis situations of the society and the country.

Cultural activity is an existence resulting from the talents, abilities, and interests of society members. Its presence is reflected in the stabilization of society's life, the realization of abilities and opportunities of talented people. At the moment, one of the important factors ensuring the development of society is the issue of spiritual activity. It is true that the issue of spiritual activity has not been studied as a separate object of research in cultural studies and spiritual studies. In fact, the development of the society, the issue of the moral standards of this society depends on the level of active or inactive spiritual activity of the citizens.

It is important that spiritual activity becomes an integral part of human life, especially at a time when globalization is rapidly increasing all over the world, changing people's minds, ways of thinking, social-political, ideological-ideological views. Spiritual activity, by its nature, is a broader concept than cultural activity.

Because this phenomenon is a force that strengthens people's ancient values such as morality, humanity, justice.

In other words, if cultural activity makes society's life more beautiful, if it allows people to reveal their talents and abilities, then spiritual activity is an important factor that ensures moral, socio-spiritual stability of society. In this sense, spiritual activity can be understood as a set of spiritual relations, processes, communication and communication of an individual, nation and society, a goal aimed at morally purifying all aspects of social life, and a state of achieving it. The rational core of spiritual activity is the educational process. The social and spiritual life of our people cannot be imagined without the processes of education and moral reform. No matter which period of our national history we look at, we can see that in all of them, our national education and morals were improved and refined, taking into account the characteristics of that period. For example, our great-grandfather Abdulla Avloni says: “The most important thing for people is the education of morals that gives them a noble and high level. In the previous lesson, we said that there is a difference between training and teaching, because: a learner means a knower, and a learner means a doer”.

This idea can be said to reveal the true purpose of the phenomenon of education. The fact is that in today's rapidly developing world of information, there is nothing that young and old do not know or read. We are aware of everything, from the simple education process to advanced technologies, from solving livelihood problems to global geopolitical problems. In other words, as Abdullah Awlani noted, we are all knowledgeable, but we are imperfect when it comes to acting on what we know. The phenomenon of morals and education should become a means of eliminating this disproportion. From this point of view, spiritual activity becomes an important factor protecting any country and society from ideological and ideological threats.

In the matter of the formation and satisfaction of spiritual and cultural requirements, it is necessary to determine whether the creation of spiritual and cultural products, values, works is primary in this process, or is it the requirement of the individual and society to master them? It should be noted that this is a very

important issue. In answering this question, it is of particular importance to determine how to approach these processes when reacting to the issue of culture, spirituality, and requirements in general.

In an open, democratic society, the emergence of the ability of a person to demonstrate his talents, their socialization, meeting the requirements reflected in various normative documents adopted by this society, following social values, and getting rid of the state of alienation from society and the state, the spiritual requirements of each person have priority. requires giving. This increases the social importance of spiritual requirements. Thus, in the current conditions of social development, cultural and spiritual requirements are becoming one of the important and decisive factors in the development of any state and society. Various teachings and ideas inherited by scholars and thinkers from the East, especially from Central Asia, have a special place in this. Their ideas that cultural and spiritual requirements are the force that unites the society and forms the mood of socialization in people have not lost their scientific and practical importance even today. A new spiritual space, a strong spirituality, which is one of the most important factors in the establishment of an enlightened state in the new Uzbekistan, can actually be created during the formation and satisfaction of the cultural and spiritual requirements of the individual.

References

1. Shavkat Mirziyoyev. Insonparvarlik, ezgulik va bunyodkorlik – milliy g‘oyamizning poydevoridir. – Toshkent, “Tasvir”, 2021.
2. O‘zbek tilining izohli lug‘ati. 5-tom. –Toshkent, “O‘zbekiston”, 2020.
3. Abu Nasr Forobiy. Fozil odamlar shahri. –Toshkent, “Yangi asr avlodi”, 2016.
4. Jakbarov M. Komil inson g‘oyasining tarixiy-falsafiy negizlari. – Toshkent, “Tafakkur”, 2011.

5. Бируни. Минерология: собрание сведений для познания драгоценностей. –М., 1963.
6. Shayx Muhammad Sodiq Muhammad Yusuf. Tasavvuf haqida tasavvur. – Toshkent, “Sharq”, 2012.
7. Najmiddin Komilov. Tasavvuf. Birinchi kitob. –Toshkent, “Yozuvchi”, 1996.
8. Akmal Saidov. Attorshunoslik. –Toshkent, “Sharq”, 2013.
9. Abdurahim Erkayev. Ma’naviyatshunoslik. 2-kitob. –Toshkent, “Ma’naviyat”, 2018.
10. Abdulla Avloniy. So‘ylasang, so‘yla, yaxshi so‘zlardin. – Toshkent, “Ma’naviyat”, 2022.